

High Performance Au-decorated ZnO 2D-Nanosheets for NO₂ Gas Sensing Applications

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Abstract:

Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) is a highly toxic environmental pollutant, which is mainly produced by emissions from power plants, combustion engines and automobiles and can cause serious health hazards. Therefore, detection of such harmful pollutants is a serious demand for environmental monitoring. Herein, we report the synthesis, characterization and evaluation of NO₂ gas sensor properties of ZnO@Au heterojunction 2D nanosheets to develop a reliable sensor that can effectively detect NO₂ at trace-level concentrations. Two-dimensional nanostructures are highly attractive for fabricating nanodevices due to their high surface-to-volume ratio and compatibility with device design. Structural and morphological analyses have been carried out using XRD, HR-TEM, UV-Visible and fluorescence spectrum. The temperature dependent *I-V* characteristic of 2D ZnO-Au nanosheets was used to explore the electron transport properties of the nanosheets. The gas sensing properties of the ZnO nanosheets were analyzed which exhibited high sensitivity for detecting NO₂ at lower working temperature. The catalytic behaviour of Au found to enhance the sensor response towards NO₂.

Keywords: ZnO Nanosheets, heterojunctions, NO₂ gas sensor, Au-catalytic behaviour.

Figure: (a) TEM image of ZnO@Au nanosheets, inset shows corresponding SAED pattern, (b) HR-TEM image of ZnO nanosheets

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